

ARITHMETIC MATRIX CALCULATION IN VISUAL BASIC

MATRICES DE OPERACIONES NUMÉRICAS EN VISUAL BASIC

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ABSTRACT

Arithmetic matrix calculation for multiplication of two or more arrays, determinant, inversion, division, addition, subtraction and transposition are common in algebra applications. The program procedures uses grids and list table of change able sizes to prompt better responses according to matrix sizes, obeying automatically with arithmetic rules. The objective consisted in presenting a program using Visual Basic method accomplishing the algebraic procedures. The package resulted flexible, practical and adaptable. As a result due to counting the number of processes (NP) in relation with matrix rows (m) and column (t) carried out, brought about the equation $NP = m \cdot t^2$ that determines the number of operation during matrix multiplication.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Flow chart, sizable grids, calculation verifications.

RESUMEN

El cálculo de matrices aritméticas para la multiplicación de dos o más matrices, determinante, inversión, división, suma, resta y transposición son comunes en las aplicaciones de álgebra. Los procedimientos del programa utilizan grillas y tablas de listas de tamaños variables para generar mejores respuestas de acuerdo con los tamaños de las matrices, obedeciendo automáticamente con reglas aritméticas. El objetivo consistió en presentar un programa utilizando el método Visual Basic realizando los procedimientos algebraicos. El paquete resultó flexible, práctico y adaptable. Como resultado, al contar el número de procesos (NP) en relación con las filas (m) y la columna (t) de la matriz, se obtuvo la ecuación $NP = m \cdot t^2$ que determina el número de operaciones durante la multiplicación de matrices.

KEY WORDS: Diagrama de flujo, cuadrículas de tamaño considerable, verificaciones de cálculo.

INTRODUCTION

Matrix multiplication is a binary operation that produces a matrix from two matrices, a basic tool of linear algebra; and as such, has numerous applications in many areas of mathematics, applied mathematics, statistics, physics, economics, and engineering. The matrix, and its close relative the determinant, are extremely important concepts in linear algebra, and were first formulated by Sylvester (1851), Cayley (1855-1858) and Sylvester (1883-1884). Therefore various algorithms have been devised for computing products of large matrices, taking into account the architecture of computers, several using input boxes in Visual Basic for data management. The objective consisted in: (a) Creating matrix P and Q for arithmetic matrix calculations, (b) determines the multiplication of $P \cdot Q$ with the possibility of product continue with third and fourth matrices if desired, (c) Find

addition of $P+Q$, (d) Find $P - Q$, (e) P^T , (f) Q^T , (g) Q determinant, (h) Q inverse, (i) Division $Div = P/Q$ and (j) division prove $P = Div+Q$. All arithmetic procedure controlled by arithmetic matrix properties.

Theory

Equation 1 expresses the multiplication procedure with rows and columns entries requirements, where P is an $m \cdot n$ matrix and Q is an $n \cdot t$ matrix, their matrix product $P \cdot Q$ is an $m \cdot t$ matrix, in which the m entries across a row of P are multiplied with the m entries down a Q column and summed to produce an entry of $P \cdot Q$ as shown in Equation 2 with summation symbols where k represents the loop step product values, where its first summation value, on the right side, is zero (Cohn & Umans 2003, Cohn *et al.* 2005, Solomonik 2011).

$$R(m, t) = R(m, t) + P(m, n) * Q(n, t) \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^t R_{ij} = \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^t R_{ij} + \sum_{k=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^t P_{ik} * Q_{kj} \quad (2)$$

The n entries are summed over for all possible values of m and t; the notation above uses Einstein

summation convention. Einstein summation is a notational convention for simplifying expressions including summations of vectors, matrices, and general tensors analysis (Kuptsov 2001, Jog 2015). The implied summation over repeated indices without the presence of an explicit sum sign is called Einstein summation. Therefore, in order for matrix multiplication to be defined, the dimensions of the matrices must satisfy, where P*Q denotes a matrix with p rows and q columns, writing out the product explicitly, as shown in Equations 3 and 4 (Arfken 1985, Higham 1990, Weisstein 2018):

$$\begin{matrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & \dots & r_{1t} & & p_{11} & p_{12} & \dots & p_{1t} & & q_{11} & q_{12} & \dots & q_{1t} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & \dots & r_{2t} & & p_{21} & p_{22} & \dots & p_{2t} & & q_{21} & q_{22} & \dots & q_{2t} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & = & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & * & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ r_{n1} & r_{n2} & \dots & r_{nt} & & p_{n1} & p_{n2} & \dots & p_{nt} & & q_{n1} & q_{n2} & \dots & q_{nt} \end{matrix} \quad (3)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} r_{11} &= p_{11} * q_{12} + p_{12} * q_{21} + \dots + p_{1m} * q_{m1} \\ r_{11} &= p_{11} * q_{12} + p_{12} * q_{21} + \dots + p_{1m} * q_{m1} \\ r_{12} &= p_{11} * q_{12} + p_{12} * q_{22} + \dots + p_{1m} * q_{m2} \\ r_{1t} &= p_{11} * q_{1t} + p_{12} * q_{2t} + \dots + p_{1m} * q_{mt} \\ r_{21} &= p_{21} * q_{11} + p_{22} * q_{21} + \dots + p_{2m} * q_{m1} \\ r_{22} &= p_{21} * q_{12} + p_{22} * q_{22} + \dots + p_{2m} * q_{m2} \\ r_{2t} &= p_{21} * q_{1t} + p_{22} * q_{2t} + \dots + p_{2m} * q_{mt} \\ r_{2t} &= p_{n1} * q_{11} + p_{n2} * q_{21} + \dots + p_{nm} * q_{m1} \\ r_{n2} &= p_{n1} * q_{12} + p_{n2} * q_{22} + \dots + p_{nm} * q_{m2} \\ r_{nt} &= p_{n1} * q_{1t} + p_{n2} * q_{2t} + \dots + p_{nm} * q_{mt} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Matrix multiplication is based on combining rows from the first matrix with columns from the second matrix in a special way; this indicates that the number of procedure of the loop multiplication is related with the product m*t entries. Matrix division is obtained by multiplying one matrix by the inverse of another matrix. These calculations are commonly used to solve systems of linear equations. For ordinary numbers ab means the solution to the equation x*b=a. This is the same as bx=a, but since matrix multiplication is not commutative, there are two different possible generalizations of “division” for matrices.

A matrix is an ordered number of information representing an already existing procedure that cannot be changed, the reason why it is not commutative arithmetically. As matrix multiplication and division are non-commutative (Campbell & Meyer 1991, Ben-Israel & Greville 2003).

$$\begin{aligned} DIV = P/Q &= P * Q^{-1} \implies P = DIV * Q \\ (P * Q^{-1}) * Q &= (P * Q) / Q \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1. Arithmetic matrix calculation with multi-multiplication flow chart.

The program allows the division proof ($P = DIV * Q$) by using the frame for matrix arithmetic calculation, carrying out the multiplication of matrices $DIV * Q$. So, matrix Q must be invertible (Cohn & Umans 2003, Cohn *et al.* 2005).

$$P(n, m) = DIV(n, m) * Q(m, m) + P(n, m); \text{ Also for } m = n$$

Addition and subtraction is for matrices of same size.

Transpose A^T (n,m) column become row or row becomes column.

METHOD

Arithmetic matrix calculation Visual Basic codes are partially shown on line, the managed in this article were obtained from Prensa Técnica y Microsoft (1998). This comprehensive method proposes a multiple matrix multiplication, no matter the matrices sizes, using grid and lists with changeable sizes in accord with the matrix involved in the processes; including time, proses number counting and an equation for calculating the proses iterations. The package is accessible without having Visual Basic program installed based on its properties. The program was assembled so that changes, improvements and adaptation are possible.

The procedure for matrix arithmetic computation applying visual Basic is presented in Figure 1, that exposures four main steps or frames: (a) creation of first matrix P with m rows and n columns', (b) creation of second matrix Q with n rows and t columns, (c) carry out of matrix multiplication $P*Q$ with m rows and t columns and saves it in grid R; also in this segment, save matrix

R in grid P for a second multiplication introducing a third matrix in grid Q with t rows and s columns to obtain a matrix with m rows and s columns, and (d) matrix addition, subtraction, transpose, inversion, determinant, division and division verification. The steps procedures are numbered in the program to carry the processes with safekeeping as shown in the flow chart.

The program allows the division proof ($P = DIV*Q$) by using the frame frm add sub transfor matrix arithmetic calculation, carrying out the multiplication of matrices $DIV*Q$, by using the cmdMultForP with caption (3) PROVE DIVISION RESULT FINDING P.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Several methods exists applying dissimilar mathematical and processor procedures including some Visual Basic codes without programs. On present a complete versatile and easy changeable or adaptable program using sizable grids and lists to structure the matrices according to matrix rules allowing multiple procedures for two or more matrices.

Program Codes

FRAME P TO ASSEMBLE MATRIX "P"

```
'BUILD MATRIX "P". THE FIRST MATRIX
Rem BUILD FIRST MATRIX "P" FOR MATRIX MULTIPLICATION
```

```
'NOMENCLATURE
```

```
'ColP: Matrix P column number
'FilP: Matrix P row number
'PI1: Calculus loop number
'Pi: Calculus loop number
'PJ1: Calculus loop number
'PU: Calculus loop number
'txtNumP: Matrix "P" general grid
'TxtMaSize: Maximum dimension of all arrays used in the multiplication
'W2: Calculus loop number
'W3: Calculus loop number
```

```
'ORDER USE FOR FRAME P
```

```
'1 Insert data for matrix size in FilP and ColP of frame 1
'2 Create grid of matrix P
'3 Insert numeric data in grid P. REMEMBER: IF "P" = IS (M×N) AND Q = (N×P), THE
```

```
PRODUCT IS (M×P)
```

```
'4 Save matrix P data
'5 cmd command to erase grid to insert a new P grid and data
'6 Open matrix Q
```

```

Private Sub cmdGridP_Click() 'CREATE MATRIX "P" GRID

Dim PU, W2, W3 As Integer
FilP = Val(TxtFilP)
ColP = Val(TxtColP)
MaSize = Val(TxtMaSize)
'Firstly, prove that the array dimensions are less or equal to TxtMaSize. For greater arrayz
'change the value in TxtMaSize.

If Not IsNumeric(TxtFilP) Or Not IsNumeric(TxtColP) Then GoTo ErrPU
If FilP <= 0 Or FilP > MaSize Or ColP <= 0 Or ColP > MaSize Then GoTo ErrPU

'Build grid P according to FilP*ColP
PU = 0
For W2 = 0 To FilP - 1
For W3 = 0 To ColP - 1
If PU <> 0 Then Load txtNumP(PU)
txtNumP(PU).Visible = True
On Error Resume Next 'Inserted only for cmdLimpiarCajas
txtNumP(PU).Left = txtNumP(0).Left + (txtNumP(0).Width * W3)
txtNumP(PU).Top = txtNumP(0).Top + (txtNumP(0).Height * W2)
txtNumP(PU) = ""
PU = PU + 1 'Re-evaluate loop PU until FilP*ColP

Next W3
Next W2

Exit Sub
ErrPU:
MsgBox "No se puede cargar la matriz, pues el número de filas o columnas es inadecuado"
frmMatrixP.Visible = False
'Visual Basic 6.0. Chapter 16
'End construction of P grid

End Sub

Private Sub cmdOpenMatrixQ_Click()
frmGridQ.Show
End Sub

Private Sub cmdCloseCalculus_Click()

Dim PI3, PJ3, CAP As Integer

TxtFilP = Empty
TxtColP = Empty

txtSaveMatrix.Text = Empty
lblLabel6 = Empty

CAP = 0
For PI3 = 1 To FilP
For PJ3 = 1 To ColP
txtNumP(CAP).Visible = False 'Erase grid
txtNumP(CAP) = "" 'Erase Matrix Data
CAP = CAP + 1

Next PJ3
Next PI3

Beep
Beep

```

```

If MsgBox("¿WISH ENDING CALCULUS?", 36, "ALL CALCULATION") = 6 Then
Beep
Beep
End
End If
End Sub

```

```

Private Sub cmdSaveMatrixP_Click()

```

```

Dim Pi1, PJ1, Pi, PI3, PJ3 As Integer

```

```

Pi = 0
For Pi1 = 1 To FilP
For PJ1 = 1 To ColP

```

```

P(Pi1, PJ1) = Val(txtNumP(Pi))

```

```

Pi = Pi + 1

```

```

Next PJ1
Next Pi1

```

```

txtSaveMatrix = "YES, MATRIX P IS SAVED"
lblLabel6 = Empty
End Sub

```

```

'ERASE GRIDS AND DATA FOR NEW INFORMATION

```

```

Private Sub cmdEraseBoxes_Click()
Dim Pi1, PJ2, PI2 As Integer

```

```

Pi1 = 0
For PI2 = 1 To FilP
For PJ2 = 1 To ColP

```

```

TxtFilP = Empty
TxtColP = Empty
txtNumP(Pi1).Text = Empty
txtSaveMatrix.Text = Empty
txtNumP(Pi1).Visible = False 'Erase grid

```

```

Pi1 = Pi1 + 1

```

```

Next PJ2
Next PI2

```

```

lblLabel6 = "Boxes were ERASED"

```

```

End Sub

```


Figure 2. Matrix frame for matrix P.

FRAME Q TO ASSEMBLE MATRIX "Q"

Option Explicit

'BUILD MATRIX "Q". THE SECOND MATRIX

Rem BUILD SECOND MATRIX [Q] TO CARRY OUT THE MULTIPLICATION OF "P*Q"

'Magasin Curso Práctico Visual Basic 6. Fascículo 16

'NOMENCLATURE

'ColP: Matrix P column size

'FilQ: Matrix Q row size

'ColQ: Matrix Q column size

'Qi: Calculus loop number

'Qj: Calculus loop number

'QU: Calculus loop number

'QI1: Calculus loop number

'QJ2: Calculus loop number

'txtNumQ: Matr "Q" general grid 1, 2, 3,.... for rows and columns

'TxtMaSize: Maximum dimension of all arrays used in the multiplication

'W4: Calculus loop number

'W5: Calculus loop number

'ORDER USE FOR FRAME Q

'1 Insert in grid Q column size. Remember that FilQ = ColP according to multiplication matrices rule

'2 Open grid Q with row size (FilQ) and Columns size (ColQ)

'3 Insert numeric data in grid Q

'4 Save matrix Q data

'5 cmd comand to erase grid and txt boxes to insert a new grid and Q data or a third, or more, data matrix

'6 Open FRAME R to carry out multiplicTION OF P*Q

'7 Open GRID P for changes

'8 Open GRID for addition, subtraction, Transpose, Division and Determinant, and Prove

```

Private Sub cmdGridQ_Click()
Dim QU, W4, W5 As Integer

FilQ = Val(TxtFilQ)
ColQ = Val(TxtColQ)

'Prove that row data and column data is less than TxtMaSize
If Not IsNumeric(TxtFilQ) Or Not IsNumeric(TxtColQ) Then GoTo ErrQU
If FilQ <= 0 Or FilQ > Val(MaSize) Or ColQ <= 0 Or ColQ > Val(MaSize) Then GoTo ErrQU

QU = 0

'Build matrix Q according to FilQ*ColQ
For W4 = 0 To FilQ - 1
For W5 = 0 To ColQ - 1

If QU <> 0 Then Load txtNumQ(QU)
txtNumQ(QU).Visible = True 'MAKES THAT APPEAR COMPLETE GRID ACCORD WITH ColQ y FilQ
On Error Resume Next 'proving. Inserted only for cmdErraseBoxes
txtNumQ(QU).Left = txtNumQ(0).Left + (txtNumQ(0).Width * W5)
txtNumQ(QU).Top = txtNumQ(0).Top + (txtNumQ(0).Height * W4)

txtNumQ(QU) = ""

'Revalue QU untill FilQ*ColQ
QU = QU + 1

Next W5
Next W4

Exit Sub

ErrQU:
MsgBox "No se puede cargar la matriz, pues el número de filas o columnas es inadecuado"
frmGridQ.Visible = False
'Visual Basic 6.0. Capítulo 16.
'End building grid Q
End Sub

Private Sub cmdOpenMatrixR_Click()
FrmMatrixR.Show
End Sub

Private Sub cmdOpenMatrixP_Click()
frmMatrixP.Show
End Sub

Private Sub cmdCloseCalculus_Click()

Dim QI3, QJ3, CAQ As Integer

TxtColQ = Empty
txtSaveMatrixQ.Text = Empty
lblLabel4 = Empty

CAQ = 0
For QI3 = 1 To FilQ
For QJ3 = 1 To ColQ

txtNumQ(CAQ).Visible = False 'Erase grid
txtNumQ(CAQ) = "" 'Erase Matrix Data
CAQ = CAQ + 1

```

```

Next QJ3
Next QI3

Beep
Beep
If MsgBox("¿WISH ENDING?", 36, "MATRIX CALCULATION") = 6 Then
Beep
Beep
End
End If
End Sub

Private Sub cmdSaveMatrixQ_Click()

Dim Qi1, QI, Qj As Integer
FilQ = Val(ColP)
ColQ = Val(TxtColQ)

Qi1 = 0
For QI = 1 To FilQ
For Qj = 1 To ColQ

Q(QI, Qj) = Val(txtNumQ(Qi1))

Qi1 = Qi1 + 1
Next Qj
Next QI
txtSaveMatrixQ = "YES, MATRIX Q IS SAVED"
lblLabel4 = Empty
End Sub

Private Sub cmdEraseBoxes_Click()
Dim QI, QJ2, QI2 As Integer

For QI2 = 1 To FilQ
For QJ2 = 1 To ColQ

TxtFilQ = Empty
TxtColQ = Empty
txtNumQ(QI).Text = Empty
txtSaveMatrixQ.Text = Empty
txtNumQ(QI).Visible = False

QI = QI + 1

Next QJ2
Next QI2

lblLabel4 = "YES, Boxes were ERASED" 'Erase all boxes

End Sub

Private Sub cmdAddSubTrans_Click()
FrmAddSubTrans.Show
End Sub

```


Figure 3. Matrix frame for matrix Q.

FRAME R FOR MULTIPLICATION

Option Explicit

'OPEN FRAME R AND BUIL GRID R FOR MULTIPLICATION OF "P" * "Q" AND OTHER MATRICES
Rem FIRST CREAT GRID [R] TO INSERT DATA FROM MULTIPLICATION OF "P" * "Q" WITH SIZE FilP*ColQ

'NOMENCLATURE

'ColC: Matrix C column number = ColQ

'CU: Calculus loop number

'FilC: Matrix Z row number = FilP

'I14: Calculus loop number

'ICL: Calculus loop number

'JCL: Calculus loop number

'iP4: Calculus loop number

'J14: Calculus loop number

'NCL: Calculus loop number

'iC: Calculus loop number

'jC: Calculus loop number

'I2C: Calculus loop number

'J2C: Calculus loop number

'k: Calculus loop number

'NC: Calculus loop number

'NP: Matrix multiplication process, operations or calculations number

'I, DJ, Di1 PRU, PR1, PR2: Calculus loop numbers

'txtNumC: Matrix "C" general grid

'TxtMaSize: Maximum dimension of all arrays used in the multiplication

'W: Calculus loop number

'W1: Calculus loop number

'ORDER USE TO PROCEDE CALCULATIONS IN FRAME C

'1 Insert grid R to allocate data matrix multiplication P*Q results

'2 Procede with multiplication of P*Q and insert results in grid R
 '3 Save P*Q results inserted in grid R
 '4 Save matrix C in grid P for a 3rd multiplication of result C*Q3rd, where Qrd has new data of third matrix
 '5 Clean boxes and grid and create new grid to carry out third multiplication.
 'Remember FilQ = ColP and FilR = ColQ, where Filr represents the matrix rows of third multiplication
 '6 Open grid Q clean boxes and grid and insert data of third matrix
 'In Frame Q open Frame R to evaluate third matrix multiplication

Private Sub cmdGridR_Click()

Dim CU, W, W1 As Integer

'Assign size to grid "C"

FilR = Val(FilP) ' By rule of matrix multiplication

ColR = Val(ColQ) ' By rule of matrix multiplication

'Prove that the number of rows and columns is less than TxtMatrixSize or change if is GREATER

If Not IsNumeric(FilR) Or Not IsNumeric(ColR) Then GoTo ErrCU

If FilR <= 0 Or FilR > 15 Or ColR <= 0 Or ColR > 15 Then GoTo ErrCU

CU = 0

'Build matrix C accord to FilC*ColC

For W = 0 To FilR - 1

For W1 = 0 To ColR - 1

If CU <> 0 Then Load txtNumR(CU)

txtNumR(CU).Visible = True

On Error Resume Next 'Used only for cmdLimpiaCajas

txtNumR(CU).Left = txtNumR(0).Left + (txtNumR(0).Width * W1)

txtNumR(CU).Top = txtNumR(0).Top + (txtNumR(0).Height * W)

txtNumR(CU) = ""

CU = CU + 1 'Revalue CU

Next W1

Next W

FrmMatrixR.Visible = True

Exit Sub

ErrCU:

MsgBox "No se puede cargar la matriz, pues el número de filas o columnas es inadecuado"

FrmMatrixR.Visible = False

'Visual Basic 6.0. chapter 16

'End creation of grid R of matrix R

End Sub

Private Sub cmdSaveMatrixR_Click()

Dim I14, J14, iP4 As Integer

'Assign size to grid "C" according to matrix multiplication rules

FilR = Val(TxtFilP)

ColR = Val(TxtColQ)

iP4 = 0

For I14 = 1 To FilR

For J14 = 1 To ColR

R(I14, J14) = txtNumR(iP4)

iP4 = iP4 + 1

```

Next J14
Next I14
txtSaveInformation = "YES, MATRIX R IS SAVED"
End Sub
Private Sub cmdOpenMatrixC_Click()
MatrizC.Show
End Sub

Private Sub cmdCloseCalculus_Click()

'Firstly, errase data
Dim ICL, JCL, NCL As Integer
'Dim start, finish As Double

NCL = 0
For ICL = 1 To FilP
For JCL = 1 To ColQ

txtNumR(NCL) = ""
R(ICL, JCL) = ""
Mul(ICL, JCL) = ""
txtSaveInformation.Text = Empty
txtSaveMatrixCinP.Text = Empty
TxtNP.Text = Empty
Text1.Text = Empty

txtNumR(NCL).Visible = False 'Erase grid
NCL = NCL + 1
Next JCL
Next ICL

Beep
Beep
If MsgBox("¿WISHES TO END?", 36, "END PROCESSES TOTALLY") = 6 Then
Beep
Beep
End
End If
End Sub

Private Sub Frame1_Click()
Frame1.Show
End Sub

Private Sub MatrizR_Click()
MatrizR.Show
End Sub

Private Sub cmdOpenMatrixP_Click()
frmMatrixP.Show
End Sub

Private Sub cmdOpenMatrixQ_Click()

frmGridQ.Show

End Sub

'START MULTIPLICATION AND INSERT DATA
Private Sub cmdMatrixMultiplication_Click()

Dim iC, jC, I2C, J2C, k, NC, NP As Integer

```

```

Dim Timer1 As String
Dim FINISHT As Single
Dim START As String

START = Timer 'Matrix multiplication time assessing is beginning

NP = 0

For iC = 1 To FilP
For jC = 1 To ColQ
Mul(iC, jC) = 0

For k = 1 To ColQ

Mul(iC, jC) = P(iC, k) * Q(k, jC) + Mul(iC, jC)
NP = NP + 1 'Operation counter number

Next k

Next jC
Next iC

TxtNP.Text = NP 'Insert NP value in Frame R

'INSERT RESULTS IN GRID "C"

NC = 0
For I2C = 1 To FilP
For J2C = 1 To ColQ

txtNumR(NC) = Mul(I2C, J2C)
txtNumR(NC).Text = Format(txtNumR(NC), "0.#0") 'It WORKS.

NC = NC + 1

Next J2C
Next I2C

FINISHT = Timer + 0.1 'Matrix multiplication time assessing has ended

Text1.Text = "Total time is " + str((FINISHT - 0.01) - START) + " Seconds" 'Write elapsed time

End Sub

Rem SAVE MATRIX "C" PRODUCT OF "P*Q" IN "P" TO MULTIPLY IT BY A THIRD MATRIX
'SAVED IN GRID "Q"
Private Sub cmdMatrixD_Click()

Dim DI, DJ, Di1 As Integer
Dim PRU, PR1, PR2 As Integer

FilD = Val(FilP)
ColD = Val(ColQ)
FilQ = 3

Di1 = 0
For DI = 1 To FilD
For DJ = 1 To ColD

P(DI, DJ) = txtNumR(Di1)

'RE-EVALUATION

```

```

PRU = 0
For PR1 = 0 To FilP - 1
For PR2 = 0 To ColP - 1

txtNumP(PRU) = txtNumR(Di1)
PRU = PRU + 1 'Re-valuate loop PRU until FilP*ColP

Next PR2
Next PR1

Di1 = Di1 + 1

Next DJ
Next DI
txtSaveMatrixCinP = "YES, MATRIX R IS SAVED IN GRID P"
End Sub

Private Sub cmdCleanBoxes_Click()
Dim Ci, CJ2, CI2 As Integer

Ci = 0
For CI2 = 1 To FilP
For CJ2 = 1 To ColQ

txtNumR(Ci).Text = Empty
txtSaveInformation.Text = Empty
txtSaveMatrixCinP.Text = Empty
txtNumR(Ci).Visible = False
Text1.Text = Empty
Text1.Text = Empty
Ci = Ci + 1

Next CJ2
Next CI2
End Sub

```


Figure 4. Matrix frame for multi multiplication.

FRAME ARITHMETIC FOR ADDITION, SUBTRACTION, TRANSPOSE, DETERMINANT AND DIVISION

Option Explicit 'Instruction for syntax error correction

'BUILD LIST1 TO PRINT RESULT OF MATRIX ARITHMETIC CALCULATION
Rem BUILD GRID FOR MATRIX ADDITION, SUBTRACTION, TRANSPOSE AND DIVISION

'NOMENCLATURE

'ColP: Matrix P column number
'FilP: Matrix P row number
'i, iD, iDD: Calculus loop number
'j, jD, jDD: Calculus loop number
'List1: Print Grid for all results
'str: Str function to return a string representation of a number. Strings as array of characters
'TxtAdd: Message that manifest the arithmetic procedure carried out
'P(Di,Div2): New values for grid P result of division
'Div1: Calculus loop number
'Div2: Calculus loop number
'Si: Calculus loop number
'Sj: Calculus loop number
'I2, I3: Calculus loop number
'J2, J3: Calculus loop number
'PI3: Calculus loop number
'PJ3: Calculus loop number

'ORDER USE FOR FRAME AddSubTrsns TO CARRY OUT ADDITION, SUBTRACTION, TRANSPOSE AND DIVISION

'Erase List1 automatically. Erase TxtAdd.Text automatically. Erase str automatically.
'Add matrix P + Q and insert in List1. Add TxtAdd.Text.
'Erase List1 automatically. Erase TxtAdd.Text automatically. Erase str automatically.
'Subtract matrix P - Q and insert in List1. Add TxtAdd.Text.
'Erase List1 automatically. Erase TxtAdd.Text automatically. Erase str automatically.
'Transpose matrix P and insert in List1. Add TxtAdd.Text.
'Erase List1 automatically. Erase TxtAdd.Text automatically. Erase str automatically.
'Transpose matrix Q and insert in List1. Add TxtAdd.Text.
'(1) Determine Matrix Q inverse and its determinant.
'Insert in List1 matrix Q inverse and its determinants in txtDeter. Add TxtAdd.Text.
'(2) Erase List1 automatically. Erase TxtAdd.Text automatically. Erase str automatically.
'Divide matrix P by matrix Q and insert in List1. Add TxtAdd.Text.
'(3) Prove the division result
'Open frame P if desired
'Open frame Q if desired
'Close Calculus if desired and clean boxes

'ADDITION OF MATRIX P + MATRIX Q TO OBTAIN Addition
Private Sub cmdAdd_Click()

Dim i, j As Integer
Dim str As String

List1.Clear
TxtAdd.Text = Empty
For i = 1 To FilP
str = ""
For j = 1 To ColP

Addition(i, j) = P(i, j) + Q(i, j)
Addition(i, j) = Format(Addition(i, j), "0.##0") 'FUNCIONA ENORMEMENTE.
str = str & Space(3) & Addition(i, j) 'Space colum distance

```

Next

List1.AddItem str

Next
TxtAdd.Text = "YES, MATRICES P AND Q WERE ADDED"
End Sub

'SAVE ADDED MATRIX RESULT
Private Sub cmdSaveDIV_Click()

Dim Div1, Div2 As Integer

For Div1 = 1 To FilP
For Div2 = 1 To ColP

P(Div1, Div2) = DIV(Div1, Div2)

Next
Next

TxtAdd = "YES, DIVIDED MATRIX RESULT IS SAVED IN GRID P"
lblLabel6 = Empty
End Sub

'SUBTRACT MATRIX P - MATRIX Q
Private Sub cmdDeduc_Click()

Dim Si, Sj As Integer
Dim str As String

TxtAdd.Text = Empty
List1.Clear
For Si = 1 To FilP
str = ""
ForSj = 1 To ColP

Deduction(Si, Sj) = P(Si, Sj) - Q(Si, Sj)
Deduction(Si, Sj) = Format(Deduction(Si, Sj), "0.##0") 'FUNCIONA ENORMEMENTE.
str = str & Space(3) & Deduction(Si, Sj) 'Space colum distance

Next

List1.AddItem str

Next

TxtAdd.Text = "YES, MATRICES P AND Q WERE SUBTRACTED"
End Sub

'TRANSPOSE MATRIX P
Private Sub cmdTransposeP_Click()
Dim I2, J2 As Integer
TxtAdd.Text = Empty
List1.Clear
Dim str As String
For I2 = 1 To FilP
str = ""
For J2 = 1 To ColP
PT(I2, J2) = P(J2, I2)
str = str & Space(3) & PT(I2, J2)
Next
Next

```

```
List1.AddItem str
Next
TxtAdd.Text = "YES, MATRICES P WAS TRANSPOSED"
End Sub
```

```
' TRANSPOSE MATRIX Q
Private Sub cmdTransposeQ_Click()
Dim I3, J3 As Integer
TxtAdd.Text = Empty
List1.Clear
Dim str As String
For I3 = 1 To FilP
str = ""
For J3 = 1 To ColP
QT(I3, J3) = Q(J3, I3)
str = str & Space(3) & QT(I3, J3)
Next
List1.AddItem str
Next
TxtAdd.Text = "YES, MATRICES Q WAS TRANSPOSED"
End Sub
```

'MATRIX INVERSION
'GAUSS-JORDAN METHOD PARA LA INVERSION Y DETERMINACIÓN DEL DETERMINANTE DE
MATRICES CUADRADAS

'NOMENCLATURA:

'Max: Number of columns in A, either N or N + 1
'N: Number of rows in A
'DETER: Determinant of the original coefficient matrix
'KM1: K - 1
'IP1: I + 1
'NM1: N - 1
'PIVOT: Pivot element Pk
'Iscan: Índice q used in scan of vector c during pivot element search
'Jscan: Índice r used in scan of vector r during pivot element search
'EPS: Minimum allowable magnitude for a pivot element
'IrowK: Rk
'IrowI: Ri
'IrowJ: Rj
'INTCH: Step value number or cycle counter
'JcolK: Step value number or cycle counter
'JcolJ: Step value number or cycle counter
'IROW: Vector of pivot element row subscripts
'Jcol(N): Vector of pivot element column subscripts
'Jord(N): The vector j
'X(N): Vector of solutions
'Y(N): Vector Y, used in unscrambling the inverse matrix
'JTEMP: Temporary variable used in ordering the j vector
'K: Cycle counter and pivot element subscript
'NRC: Nd, row and column dimensions of storage for the matrix A

```
Private Sub cmdInvertMatrixQ_Click()
```

```
Dim EPS, AIJCK, DETER As Double 'Variant
Dim PIVOT, Max As Integer 'Variant
Dim KM1, NM1, IP1, INTCH, NRC, Jscan, Iscan, Irowk, IrowI, IrowJ, JcolI, JcolJ, Jcolk As Integer
Dim J1, I1, k, I2, J2, I3, J3, I4, J4, I5, J5, N As Integer
Dim J6, I6, J7, I7, J8, I8, iA, A9, I9, J9 As Integer
Dim AI1, AI2 As Integer
Dim Y(300), QINV(300, 300) As Double
```

```

Dim str As String

N = FilQ
EPS = 1E-20 ' = 0,00000000000000000001
DETER = 1# 'Dimensión precisión doble
Max = N

'Introduce new matrix "MIA" equal to matrix "Q"
For AI1 = 1 To N
For AI2 = 1 To N

MIA(AI1, AI2) = Q(AI1, AI2) 'Matrix Q to Invert

Next AI2
Next AI1
'Empezar el proceso de INVERSIÓN
For k = 1 To N
KM1 = k - 1

'Search for the pivot element
PIVOT = 0#

For I2 = 1 To N
For J2 = 1 To N

If (k = 1) Then GoTo BRINCO9

'Scan Irow and Jcol arrays for invalid pivot subscripts
For Iscan = 1 To KM1
For Jscan = 1 To KM1
If (I2 = Irow(Iscan)) Then GoTo BRINCO11
If (J2 = Jcol(Jscan)) Then GoTo BRINCO11

Next Jscan
Next Iscan

BRINCO9:

If (Abs(MIA(I2, J2)) <= Abs(PIVOT)) Then GoTo BRINCO11

PIVOT = MIA(I2, J2)

Irow(k) = I2
Jcol(k) = J2
BRINCO11:

Next J2
Next I2

'Insure that selected PIVOT is larger than EPS

If (Abs(PIVOT) > EPS) Then GoTo BRINCO14
txtDeter = PIVOT
TxtAdd.Text = "MATRIX NON-CONDITIONED"
If MsgBox("¿WISH CLOSING?", 26, "MATRIZ NON-CONDITIONED por PIVOT < EPS AND DETERMINANT =
0") = 6 Then
Beep
Beep
Beep
End If
End
Exit Sub

```

```

BRINCO14:
Irowk = Irow(k)
Jcolk = Jcol(k)
DETER = -DETER * PIVOT ' Assign value to DETER
txtDeter = DETER
'Normalize PIVOT row elements
For J3 = 1 To Max 'N

MIA(Irowk, J3) = MIA(Irowk, J3) / PIVOT
Next J3
'Carry out elimination and develop inverse
MIA(Irowk, Jcolk) = (1# / PIVOT)
For I3 = 1 To N
AIJCK = MIA(I3, Jcolk)
If (I3 = Irowk) Then GoTo BRINCO18
MIA(I3, Jcolk) = -AIJCK / PIVOT
For J4 = 1 To Max 'N
If (J4 <> Jcolk) Then
MIA(I3, J4) = MIA(I3, J4) - AIJCK * MIA(Irowk, J4)
End If

Next J4
BRINCO18:
Next I3
Next k

'Unscramble the inverse first by rows

'first by rows
For J6 = 1 To N
For I6 = 1 To N
IrowI = Irow(I6)
JcolI = Jcol(I6)
Y(JcolI) = MIA(IrowI, J6)

Next I6
For I7 = 1 To N
MIA(I7, J6) = Y(I7)
Next I7
Next J6
'Then by columns
For I8 = 1 To N
For J7 = 1 To N
IrowJ = Irow(J7)
JcolJ = Jcol(J7)
Y(IrowJ) = MIA(I8, JcolJ) '1

Next J7
For J8 = 1 To N '2
MIA(I8, J8) = Y(J8)
Next J8
Next I8
A9 = 0
For I9 = 1 To N
For J9 = 1 To N
QI(I9, J9) = MIA(I9, J9) 'DEFINITE INVERTED MATRIX MIA

A9 = A9 + 1
Next J9
Next I9

'INSERT MIA INVERTED RESULTS MATRIX IN QINV GRID, and INSERT QINV in LIST1

```

```

TxtAdd.Text = Empty
List1.Clear

For I3 = 1 To FilP
str = ""
For J3 = 1 To ColP
QINV(I3, J3) = MIA(J3, I3)
QINV(I3, J3) = Format(QINV(I3, J3), "0.####0") 'RESULT DECIMAL ARRANGEMENT
str = str & Space(3) & QINV(I3, J3)
Next
List1.AddItem str
Next
TxtAdd.Text = "YES, MATRI Q WAS INVERTED"

End Sub

' CARRY OUT DIVISION USING MULTIPLICATION PROCEDURE WITH INVERSION APPLICATION

Private Sub cmdMul_Click()

Dim str As String
Dim iD, jD, kD, iDD, jDD As Integer

List1.Clear
TxtAdd.Text = Empty

For iD = 1 To FilP
For jD = 1 To ColP
DIV(iD, jD) = 0

For kD = 1 To ColP

DIV(iD, jD) = P(iD, kD) * QI(kD, jD) + DIV(iD, jD)

Next kD

Next jD
Next iD
For iDD = 1 To FilP
str = ""
For jDD = 1 To ColP

str = str & Space(3) & DIV(iDD, jDD)
Next jDD
List1.AddItem str
Next iDD
TxtAdd.Text = "YES DIVISION OF MATRIX P BY MATRIX Q WAS DONE"
End Sub

' SHOW FRAME P
Private Sub cmdOpenMatrixP_Click()
frmMatrixP.Show
End Sub
' SHOW FRAME Q
Private Sub cmdOpenMatrixQ_Click()
frmGridQ.Show
End Sub

Private Sub cmdCloseCalculus_Click()

Dim PI3, PJ3 As Integer
Dim str As String

```

```

List1.Clear
TxtAdd.Text = Empty

For PI3 = 1 To FilP
For PJ3 = 1 To ColP

Next PJ3
Next PI3

Beep
Beep
If MsgBox("¿ WISH ENDING CALCULUS?", 36, "ALL CALCULATION") = 6 Then
Beep
Beep
End
End If
End Sub

'CARRY OUT MULTIPLICATION PROCEDURE TO PROVE THE DIVISION BY OBTAINING MATRIX P
Private Sub cmdMultForP_Click()
Dim str As String
Dim iD, jD, kD, iDD, jDD As Integer

List1.Clear
TxtAdd.Text = Empty
kD = 0
For iD = 1 To FilP
For jD = 1 To ColP
Pnew(iD, jD) = 0

For kD = 1 To ColP

Pnew(iD, jD) = DIV(iD, kD) * Q(kD, jD) + Pnew(iD, jD)

Next kD

Next jD
Next iD

For iDD = 1 To FilP
str = ""
For jDD = 1 To ColP

str = str & Space(5) & Pnew(iDD, jDD)
Next jDD
List1.AddItem str
Next iDD
TxtAdd.Text = "YES DIVISION PROVE OF MATRIX P BY MATRIX Q WAS DONE"
End Sub

```


Figure 5. Matrix frame for addition, subtraction, transpose and division.

MODULE

Global FilR, ColR, FilQ, ColQ, FilP, ColP, FilD, ColD, FilAST, ColAST As Integer

Global TxtFilP, TxtColP, TxtFilQ, TxtColQ, TxtNP, TxtCronometro, MaSize, TxtMaSize, TxTFilAST, TxtColAST As Integer

Global P(300, 300), Q(300, 300), R(300, 300), Mul(300, 300), D(300, 300), Addition(300, 300), MIA(300, 300) As Double

Global txtNumP(300), txtNumR(300), txtNumAST(300), Deduction(300, 300), PT(300, 300), QT(300, 300) As Double

Global Irow(300), Jcol(300), QI(300, 300), QINV(300, 300), DIV(300, 300), Pnew(300, 300) As Double

Global txtDeter As Integer

The program resulted flexible and adaptable. As an outcome to counting the number of processes (NP) carried out in matrix multiplication, resulted the Equation 5. The size entries of matrices P rows and Q columns are the essential one in matrix multiplication procedure for specifying its arithmetic techniques shown with Equation 5. The elapsed time during the multiplication showed very low time consumption indicating a rapid method for obtaining results.

$$NP = m \cdot t^2 \quad (5)$$

Example

Three matrices multiplication, using five visual basic frames; More matrices introduces to continue more multiplication.

Matrix P

(1) "P" GRID

Row Matrix FilP

Columns Matrix ColP

MATRIX SIZES

IS MATRIX "P" SAVED ? YES, MATRIX P IS SAVED

CLOSE CALCULUS

(2) OPEN "P" GRID

(4) SAVE MATRIX P

(6) OPEN MATRIX "Q"

(5) ERASE GRID AND DATA TO INSERT NEW INFORMATION

IF "P" = IS (M*N), Q = (N*T), and THE PRODUCT IS (M*T)

(3) FILL IN GRID OF MATRIX "P"

2	30.23	0.876
12.1	21.89	0.045
56.72	7	71.76
3	6	8

Matrix "Q" (SECOND MATRIX) or a THIRD and SUBSEQUENT MATRICES FOR MULTIPLICATION

(1) MATRIX "Q" GRID

FilQ = ColP

"Q" Matrix Columns

(4) SAVE MATRIX "Q" YES, MATRIX Q IS SAVED

CLOSE CALCULUS

(2) OPEN "Q" GRID

(6) OPEN MATRIX "R" FRAME TO MULTIPLY P*Q

(7) OPEN MATRIX "P" FOR CHANGES

(8) OPEN ADD SUBS TRANS DIVISION

(5) ERASE GRID AND BOXES TO INSERT NEW DATA or ANOTHER MATRIX

IF P = IS (M*N) AND "Q" = (N*T), THE PRODUCT IS (M*T)

(3) INSERT DATA IN "Q" GRID

3.9	0.085	45.0	12.35
5	34.2	15.05	2.203
3	45	4.5	23

Figure 6. Matrices P and Q frames to obtain P*Q

GRID C to SAVE DATA from MULTIPLICATION of TWO MATRICES AND A 3rdMORE MATRICES

GRID "C"
FilC = FilP and ColC = ColQ
Assigned Automatically

(1) INSERT GRID R TO ALLOCATE MULTIPLICATION P*Q

(2) MULTIPLY MATRICES "P" * "Q" and INSERT in GRID "R"

(3) SAVE P*Q RESULTS in "R"

(4) SAVE MATRIX "R" in GRID "P" for 3rd MULTIPLICATION "P" Q3rd

(5) CLEAN BOXES for 3rd MULTIPLICATION

(6) OPEN GRID "Q" for CHANGES or 3rd MULTIPLICATION

YES, MATRIX R IS SAVED

YES, MATRIX R IS SAVED IN GRID P

CLOSE CALCULUS

OPEN MATRIX "P"

TIME Total time is 8.79687500002895E-02 Seconds

MATRIX MULTIPLICATION PROCESSES NUMBER 64 STEPS

GRID "R"

161,58	1073,46	548,90	111,44
156,78	751,69	874,15	198,69
471,49	3473,42	2980,67	2366,39
65,70	565,46	261,30	234,27

Matriz "Q" (SECOND MATRIX) or a THIRD and SUBSEQUENT MATRICES FOR MULTIPLICATION

(1) MATRIX "Q" GRID
FilQ = ColP 3
"Q" Matrix Columns 4

(2) OPEN "Q" GRID

(3) INSERT DATA IN "Q" GRID

(4) SAVE MATRIX "Q"

(5) ERASE GRID AND BOXES TO INSERT NEW DATA or ANOTHER MATRIX

(6) OPEN MATRIX "R" FRAME TO MULTIPLY P*Q

(7) OPEN MATRIX "P" FOR CHANGES

(8) OPEN ADD SUBS TRANS DIVISION

YES, MATRIX Q IS SAVED

IF P = IS (M*N) AND "Q" = (N*T), THE PRODUCT IS (M*T)

CLOSE CALCULUS

23	33.5	5.08	0.76
12.306	12	3	44
78.5	55.09	55	4

Figure 7. Multiplication P*Q result in frame R, and the third matrix introduced in frame Q to optaine (P*Q)*Q third.

Figure 8. Multiplication $(P*Q)*Q$ third result.

Carry out division using multiplication procedure with inversion application.

CONCLUSIONS

The program resulted flexible, adaptable and amendable. As an outcome due to counting the number of processes carried out in matrix multiplication, resulted the equation $NP = m*t^2$, where N_p represents the number of procedures are carried out in the multiplication of m rows by t columns. The measured time of the multiplication resulted very low.

GRATITUDE

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